

The use of big data and artificial intelligence to reveal progression in people with multiple sclerosis

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Abstract

Rapid advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and the growing health data volume are expected to significantly impact the health sector. Neuroimmunological disorders like multiple sclerosis (MS) can particularly benefit from cutting-edge technologies due to their multifactorial nature and complex treatment. MS is a chronic, inflammatory, and degenerative disorder of the central nervous system characterised by relapsing events and increasing disability. The primary goal in MS patient care is to prevent sustained disability by addressing incomplete recovery from relapses and progression independent of relapse activity. Detecting the progressive phase is crucial for initiating appropriate treatment, although the impact of current therapies on disability progression remains partially understood. The MS Data Alliance Stakeholder Meeting 2022 aimed to facilitate and accelerate interdisciplinary conversations and collaborations between experts in the field of MS and data science to address the key question: 'How can the use of big data and artificial intelligence reveal MS progression earlier?'. This position paper summarises the key messages from the conference, emphasising the importance of a patient-centric approach, multidimensional data infrastructures, data linking, trustworthy algorithms, and education on complex data science concepts to facilitate ongoing debates on the use of cutting-edge technologies.

Main document

The use of big data and AI to reveal progression: **The need**

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is an autoimmune disease with a complex pathogenesis that is driven by inflammation and axon degeneration. The global prevalence of MS has increased from 2.1 million in 2008 to 2.8 million in 2020 and continues to rise (1). The total yearly cost of MS, estimated at €15.5 billion in Europe alone, is largely driven by progressive disability, indirect expenses such as productivity losses and informal care costs (2). Conventionally, MS has been categorised by distinct clinical descriptions into ‘relapsing-remitting’ versus ‘progressive’ MS. The latter is further divided into primary progressive MS and secondary progressive MS, based on the presence or absence of a preceding relapsing-remitting phase. Relapses are defined as episodes of neurologic dysfunction lasting at least 24 hours in the absence of fever or infection, followed by periods of remission. ‘Progressive MS’ was defined as an insidious, slowly progressive increase in neurological disability over time, usually without relapses. However, recent evidence suggests that the clinical course of MS is better viewed as a continuum, with different pathophysiological processes affecting individuals at different times and to differing extents (3).

Early detection of MS progression is imperative because progressive MS requires different treatments than relapsing MS (4). Moreover, the knowledge of their prognosis can also assist people with MS in improving their quality of life (5). Identifying and quantifying progression in MS remains a challenge specifically since signs of early progression may present differently among people with MS. This is mainly due to lesions appearing in different parts of the central nervous system, as well as underlying factors such as comorbidities, age, gender and different biological mechanisms driving inflammation and neurodegeneration (3). Diagnosis of progression is currently based on worsening of the physical examination and persistent symptoms (6). Other biomarkers for progression show limited accuracy, especially on an individual level and often combinations of several markers are necessary, which makes their use in clinical routine challenging. As a result, progression is often diagnosed retrospectively, with an estimated average 2-3-year delay (7).

Cutting-edge technologies have the potential to play a crucial role in supporting the MS community in overcoming the complexity of the disease and its treatments, particularly in addressing the challenging topic of MS progression. In November 2022, the MS Data Alliance brought together different stakeholders and pioneers in the field to discuss the current and future trends related to the use of big data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to reveal progression of MS. The MS Data Alliance is a global multi-stakeholder non-for-profit collaboration that strives to overcome the socio-technical challenges that arise when scaling-up health data, safeguarding the crucial connection between the world of data science, technology and MS. This manuscript summarises the key takeaways from this event (see Figure 1 and 2).

The use of big data and AI to reveal progression: The promise

AI can be defined as processes that allow machines or computers to exhibit intelligent behaviour. AI is typically classified into different types, such as machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL). ML gives computers the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed and refers to computational algorithms for gathering and making sense of evidence derived from large volumes of data, thereby allowing or facilitating human judgement and decision-making (8). DL are ML algorithms with a brain-like algorithmic structure called artificial neural networks and can be regarded as both a sophisticated and mathematically complex evolution of ML algorithms. To date, AI already shows promise in helping to improve diagnostic performances, workflow and cost-effectiveness. Below, some non-MS medical examples are showcased for inspiration (the current state in MS is summarised in the next section).

- **Oncology:** A recent oncology-oriented study demonstrates the development and application of an infrastructure that captures comprehensive health data longitudinally from a large institution, leading to promising prognostic AI models (9). By utilising this infrastructure, the authors also successfully employed big data to examine the influence of previously identified non-oncologic risk factors, like the Framingham cardiovascular risk score, on the mortality of cancer patients, highlighting the potential of real-world data for continuous learning and hypothesis generation. This research underlines the feasibility of AI-driven prognostic models based on large datasets, ultimately improving patient care and personalising treatment strategies.
- **Parkinson's Disease:** Parkinson's Disease (PD) was among the first diseases where sensor data collected with smartphones was shown to be relevant for assessing disease symptoms traditionally assessed by physicians. A wide range of active tests and passive monitoring, including balance (postural instability), dexterity (skill in performing tasks using hands), gait (the pattern of walking), tremor (involuntary muscle contraction and relaxation), and voice was considered relevant for the purpose. In order to leverage large-scale cross-modality smartphone features, an accurate and robust machine-learning framework was needed (10). Using multi-source ensemble learning - a methodology which combines dataset deconstruction with ensemble learning and enables participants with incomplete data to be included - increased the accuracy of remote predictions of Parkinson's Disease (11).
- **Depression:** Results from the RADAR-MDD study, an observational study which followed over 600 people with depression for up to 2 years, demonstrated that recruitment and retention in long-term remote sensing studies was feasible (12) and that depressive symptom severity was associated with diverse signals from smartphones and wearables, including Bluetooth device count data (13), sleep quality (14) and homestay derived from GPS signals (15).

- **Epilepsy:** In the case of drug-resistant focal epilepsy, currently the only possibly curative treatment option is the surgical removal of the epileptogenic brain tissue. Computer-based modelling approaches, like the virtual epileptic patient (16), are used to improve the precise delineation of the epileptogenic parts of the brain. Based on patient specific neuroimaging data a virtual copy of the brain's structure and connectivity is constructed. Equipped with a dynamical model for neural activity it can simulate seizure propagation. The parameters of the model are optimised such that the simulated resemble the empirically recorded seizure patterns. The estimated distribution of epileptogenicity can then be used to inform the pre-surgical clinical staff meeting. This approach is currently being tested in a French multi-center clinical trial called EPINOV (17).

The use of big data and AI to reveal progression: **The Past and The Present**

The use of 'Real-World Data' and AI to reveal progression

The term 'Real-World-Data' (RWD) is being used with different definitions throughout the literature. For the purpose of this paper, RWD is pragmatically defined as any data that is gathered within the context of standard care as opposed to data gathered in an experimental setting such as a randomised clinical trial. This section focuses on RWD collected through MS registries as well as electronic health records (EHRs), whereas one of the following sections elaborates on the use of data collected through wearables in a real-world context.

RWD is used increasingly to address clinical questions related to MS disease behaviour, prognosis and treatment (18). MS registries have existed for over 70 years, but have proliferated recently. Over 500.000 people with MS have contributed to registries (19), leading to treatment recommendations that guide daily practice (20). Some highlighted examples of successful large-scale collaborative efforts in the field of RWD MS data are the COVID-19 in MS Global Data Sharing Initiative (21) and the Big MS Data Network (22).

There is a large amount of literature on prognostic MS models, with several recent reviews summarising the state-of-the-art (23). Some prognostic models are, or were, at some point available as web tools. With the exception of that proposed by Tintore *et al.* (24), which focuses on conversion to MS, impact data have not been published for these tools so far. Several methodological issues, such as the lack of calibration or a possible significant bias in the cohort selection, lack of using high-dimensional data needed for sensitive predictions of progression, and lack of external validation, together with regulatory and administrative support, still obstruct implementation in real-world practice (23).

A recent (2022) systematic review (25) focused on using ML to support the discovery of biomarkers that can be measured regularly and inexpensively using non-invasive and readily-accessible techniques. This review compiled 66 studies using ML on MS data (15% of them focused on prognosis) and concluded that the majority of these studies included less than 200 patients, focused on one topic and one data source only and few reached 90% accuracy. In the current literature, most studies do not publish datasets, whereas the use of longitudinal ML modelling of MS patient trajectories has proven to improve predictions of disability progression (26).

The use of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and AI to reveal progression

Magnetic resonance imaging is a powerful tool for diagnosing and progression monitoring of MS. It is included in the diagnostic criteria for MS due to its ability to track lesion dissemination over time and space. MRI is also used to detect disease activity, evaluate treatment response, and monitor brain atrophy and new/enlarging lesions (27). However, the lack of standardisation in the acquisition of clinical images represents a major challenge in their use. Therefore, the standardisation of imaging protocols is a crucial first step moving forward, before incorporating sophisticated and complex image analyses and harmonisation methods (28).

Conventional MRI, which is commonly used in clinical practice, cannot capture the complete picture of the disease activity, also known as the “clinico-radiological paradox” (29). One possible explanation is limited sensitivity of conventional MRI in detecting the diffuse pathological changes occurring in the normal-appearing white matter and the grey matter (30). Furthermore, its dependence on factors such as imaging protocols and equipment can impede data reproducibility and comparison in follow-up and cross-sectional studies (31).

Advanced imaging techniques, such as quantitative MRI, can potentially overcome these limitations (32–35). Quantitative MRI uses MRI to measure and quantify specific parameters of interest, such as fat content, water diffusion, and tissue microstructure. Moreover, quantitative MRI can quantify the physical microstructural properties of the brain tissues in standardised units (31).

Given the unmet clinical need to find quantitative imaging biomarkers, radiomics - a computational technique of extracting large amounts of quantifiable features from medical images - is gaining interest in this field (36). The features extracted from the images such as features related to size, shape, intensity, texture etc., can be correlated with biological factors or clinical outcomes and help identify potential fast responders to DMTs (36–38).

Despite promising results (36,39–42), the use of radiomics currently faces challenges in its integration into MS clinical practice. For instance, the lack of harmonisation of MRI protocols and multi-centre studies pose significant challenges that must be addressed in order to validate its clinical utility (43), which further led to a non-recommendation in 2021 MAGNIMS-CMSC-NAIMS guidelines. ML and DL based algorithms are also of interest among researchers to predict MS disease progression (44–47).

However, they encounter issues such as biased data, unbalanced datasets, and low-quality images, which leads to limiting its value in clinical practice (48,49).

The use of digital tools and AI to reveal progression

Smartphone and wearable monitoring devices are increasingly available, opening up the possibility of studying the individual in daily life. A recent online survey (50) of healthcare professionals working in the care of people with epilepsy, MS and depression showed that the majority of healthcare professionals are positive about the benefits of the concept of remote monitoring technology to be implemented in patient care plans. Most people with MS have no experience using mobile health applications for their MS, with only a minority being current users of this technology (51). Although compliance to remote monitoring remains a challenge (52), people with MS would benefit from continuous follow-up. Individuals interact with their smartphones countless times during the day, thereby providing a variety of digital sources of data. In this way, these devices could offer a way to collect relevant data on individuals' well-being, both actively and passively (i.e. without requiring them to enter information or perform self-assessments) (53). Capturing disease-related data via smartphones and wearables in chronic diseases like MS can be useful by filling gaps between doctor's visits and providing out-of-hospital insight into their well-being and progression. Continuous data collection through wearables may reveal changes in the disease course sooner, closing the gap between hospital visits (54).

Wearables and smartphones are also equipped with multiple sensor types (e.g. accelerometer, touchscreen, microphone), and therefore provide the opportunity of extracting digital biomarkers relating to multiple symptoms. Additionally, this feature can enable active tests and passive monitoring for different tasks such as: cognitive processing (e.g. electronic Symbol Digit Modalities Test), upper extremity function (Pinching Test), Draw a Shape Test, and gait and balance (e.g. Static Balance Test, timed walking tests such as U-Turn Test, Passive Monitoring of number of steps). Recent scientific publications have showcased the use of AI and digital tools for remote monitoring of people with MS, highlighting the potential importance of these devices and softwares in MS care (55–58).

Indeed, digital health tools have recently shown their value in capturing clinical manifestation of MS in patients. Multiple medical device smartphone apps for the telemonitoring of people with MS have already been developed - e.g. Floodlight (59), iCompanion (60) and Konectom (61). To date, strategic oversight across the eHealth landscape is lacking. Likewise, very few of those tools are currently undergoing rigorous technical and clinical validations. The PROMS initiative is currently performing eHealth tools landscaping to overcome this gap. PROMS is a global multi-stakeholder initiative with key stakeholders aimed at ensuring an informed and quality participation of people with MS in the decision-making processes of research and healthcare regarding their treatments and performances, together with mapping and standardising the patient-reported outcomes (PROs) over the different

patient apps that are available for people with MS (62). Ultimately, this would lead to a more standardised PRO/clinical data collection in MS.

The use of big data and AI to reveal progression: **Future recommendations and next steps**

'It's all about the data'

AI relies on large amounts of training data and the availability of informative data labels. There is a need for multidimensional data infrastructure capturing data across the different modalities of interest. High-quality clinical characterization of individual patients is crucial for effective long-term observation and evaluation of MS. This characterization should ideally involve various signals such as symptom perception, medical imaging, clinical variables, genome sequencing, conversations with clinicians, and continuous signals from wearables (63,64). Data linkage is a major challenge, as health data is primarily unstructured and no universally accepted standardised scheme currently exists for the acquisition, documentation and evaluation of clinical data in MS (65,66). Data is collected by a variety of tools, systems, and users, leading to a variety of formats and different levels of complexity. To overcome this data heterogeneity, a combined approach of defining and incorporating data standards (e.g. SNOMED CT, MedDRa), data collection consensus recommendations and common data models like OMOP (67) is proposed, with developing and implementing cutting-edge algorithms for automated data quality assessment, enhancement and harmonisation.

Recent success stories are showcasing that large-scale collaborative efforts to address urgent questions related to MS care are possible (21). The question remains: 'How can we go beyond a project-to-project approach towards a sustainable multistakeholder MS data space?' Organising a study-a-thon (68) could be an interesting future step to stimulate open science collaborations within the field of MS. This novel approach was used to assess the long-term outcomes of prostate cancer undergoing non-interventional management and the impact of comorbidities and life expectancy (69).

Within the context of the recently launched 'European Health Data Space' (70), the European Commission is funding the development and implementation of several research infrastructure focusing on specific data types. EBRAINS is a new digital research infrastructure, created by the EU-funded Human Brain Project (71), that gathers an extensive range of data and tools for brain-related research. ELIXIR (72) focuses on the construction and operation of a sustainable infrastructure for biological information in Europe to support life science research. The European Health Data and Evidence Network (EHDEN, (73)) in collaboration with the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI, (67)) community has established an international network of research (> 3,000 collaborators across > 80 countries) and observational health databases (> 900 million unique patients) from around the world bringing us closer to the ultimate goal of generating evidence about all aspects of healthcare at scale. Although different promising initiatives exist, the

strategic oversight is challenging, and the interoperability between these different technical architectures remains questionable. In addition, extensive effort will be required to leverage these technologies towards the application of MS and make them truly operational and fit-for-purpose to deliver evidence relevant for MS care.

'It's all about the analytics'

A first requisite is that AI models obtain good performance on clinically relevant tasks and are trained on high-quality datasets. However, even when excellent performance metrics are accomplished, multiple critical technical improvements still need to be made for AI to deliver its full potential in real-world clinical practice. In this section, the need for (i) increased interpretability or explainability of AI models; (ii) increased robustness or generalizability in models; and (iii) preserving privacy of individuals is explored in more detail.

While the definition of interpretable AI is disputed, it is generally referred to as models whose decision process can be understood conceptually by a human operator. Explainable AI methods are in full development and are urgently required to help clinicians and patients to trust AI models. (74). Increased interpretability can be generated through the use of beyond state-of-the-art methodologies, such as topological visualisation to visualise high-dimensional data (75), SHapely Adaptive Explanation (SHAP) to evaluate the contribution of input features to an outcome (76) or layer-wise relevance propagation (77), or Gradient Activation Maps (78).

By robustness (or generalizability), we refer to the ability of models to comply with their prescribed behaviour under a large variety of conditions or to the degree or the model's ability to adapt properly to new, previously unseen data. Many algorithms that perform well in their training phases turn out to have much higher error rates during external or cross-validation. The high-dimensional, multimodal nature of the data is as much a curse as it is a blessing, referred to as the 'curse of dimensionality' (number of features is greater than the sample size) (79). If some conditions are not covered by a model, this should be described clearly. For instance, a model that only performs well on a specific subgroup of MS patients should only be used in that same subgroup.

The development of AI applications often raises concerns about privacy and ethical use of data. More research on federated learning methods could circumvent these limitations. Federated learning is a ML technique that trains an algorithm across multiple independent data sources, without exchanging patient-level data, thus allowing to address critical issues such as data privacy, data security, data access rights and access to distributed data (80). Even though federated learning is promising, challenges remain, such as dealing with heterogeneous data as well as reducing communication resources while enhancing convergence speed.

‘It’s all about the people’

When it comes to the use of AI into clinical practice, besides the technical barriers explained in the sections above, there are several sociological barriers that need to be overcome. Developing AI with a patient-centric and patient-driven approach is crucial. Involving people with MS early in the development process has proven to be a key driver for innovative projects. Placing the person with MS at the centre of AI development ensures that the resulting technologies align more closely with their needs and preferences, leading to greater effectiveness, efficiency, and ultimately better health outcomes (81).

For AI to have a positive benefit for patient care, it is also critical to consider its potential impact on equity. In terms of MS healthcare, remote monitoring and digital technology that deploys AI algorithms could help fulfil a need caused by a lack of specialist healthcare professionals in some settings (82). Overall, if AI can improve the accuracy and speed of diagnosis, allowing for earlier intervention and personalised treatment plans, this should reduce the variation in care experienced by people with MS. Yet, the benefits of AI-assisted technology may not be available across all types of MS healthcare settings, from specialist MS centers to general neurological practices. The availability and costs of the technology may provide a barrier in low-resource settings. A commonly highlighted problem leading to inequity caused by use of AI, is biases in the dataset used for developing and validating AI algorithms (83). If models are developed on a specific, limited population, there may be issues when applying them to patients with different demographic backgrounds. Researchers in this field must keep sight of the pathway from research to implementation to ensure that the benefits of AI reduce, rather than increase, global inequity.

Furthermore, there is a knowledge and understanding gap among different stakeholders, especially between data scientists and (bio)medical researchers. There is a need to bridge this gap to ensure effective collaboration between these two domains. The success of cutting-edge technologies is dependent on the understanding of the intrinsic processes being used during the conventional pathway by which clinicians make decisions. Incorporating expert knowledge could have the potential to reduce the amount of data required to learn the process of interest. In addition, there is a need to engage patients as well as physicians that are not involved in the development and use of it.

To make this a reality, extensive education is required. Adding courses on AI to the curriculum of (bio-)medical students would help promote this cultural change in the future. MS umbrella organisations such as the MS International Federation, the European MS Platform, the European Charcot Foundation and the different regional Committees for Treatment and Research can play a role to speed-up this process. The MS Data Alliance aspires to educate the different stakeholders on complex data science concepts and would be the ideal candidate to deliver educational materials on the use of AI in MS, in line with their recent educational program ‘How to set-up a registry’ (84).

Concluding remarks

The event by the MS Data Alliance in November 2022 highlighted how cutting-edge technologies can transform the care of people with MS. By providing a platform for diverse stakeholders, including people with MS and patient societies, to share their perspectives, the event emphasised the importance of incorporating patient voices in research and clinical practice. To ensure that the potential benefits of AI and big data are realised in a patient-centric way, we must continue to prioritise the needs and well-being of those living with MS. While AI has the potential to significantly improve patient care, there is a considerable gap between its promise and its actual impact. Progression in people with MS is a highly complex phenomenon and even defining it from a clinical perspective is still under active debate. As we transition to integrating AI and digital processes into clinical care, it is essential to invest in data governance, technical infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, and education for health workers and patients. Despite the challenges, interdisciplinary collaboration among stakeholders can generate the insights needed to address the complex question of MS progression and drive the field forward.

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Author contributions

Ilse Vermeulen, Hamza Khan and Liesbet M. Peeters took the lead in writing this manuscript based on the minutes of the MS Data Alliance event and the material provided by all speakers in preparation of the event. As speakers, panellists, or moderators, all other co-authors actively participated in the event and contributed to the manuscript by providing content, comments, and suggestions.

Competing interests

Liesbet M. Peeters and Ilse Vermeulen have no conflict to report related to this work other than being the chair and the coordinator of the MS Data Alliance initiative, receiving funding from a range of corporate sponsors, including Biogen, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Janssen Pharmaceuticals, Merck, Novartis, and Roche.

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Figure 1: Building blocks to ensure data-driven insights related to progression of multiple sclerosis

Figure 2: The roadmap towards revealing MS progression through better use of data and artificial intelligence